

Branched DPS-QKD Employing a WDM-Compatible Silicon Micro-Ring Resonator as Shared Quantum State Analyser

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Abstract We prove micro-ring resonator assisted DPS-QKD as multi-wavelength alternative to delay-interferometer based implementations. We show wavelength-agnostic generation of secure keys over 13 WDM channels ranging from 1534.3 to 1555.3nm. We further demonstrate simultaneous QKD operation over 12.8km, for which two users shared the state analyser. ©2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The security of the currently employed asymmetric cryptography schemes is threatened by the rapid development of quantum computers, which has recently surpassed >1000 physical qubits [1] at ever increasing error-correcting codecs [2]. This calls for new approaches to secure communications, which can be provided by quantum key distribution (QKD). The current roll-out of QKD is mainly focused on early adopters where security is of the highest importance, as required in the governmental and financial sectors [3]. To achieve a more pervasive deployment closer to the residential user, QKD needs to demonstrate a reduced complexity burden and attractive cost-credentials. Photonic circuit integration is paramount [4,5] to enable miniaturization and cost reductions. The conceptual simplicity of differential phase shift (DPS) QKD [6,7], where micro-ring resonators (MRR) [8] yield compact state analyzers, offers a miniaturization path beyond current footprints [9].

In this work, we expand the cost advantages inherent to miniaturized QKD optics by introducing further cost-sharing by a centralized, MRR-assisted DPS-QKD receiver. We show simultaneous C-band quantum state analysis compatible with wavelength division multiplexed (WDM) quantum channels in an access-scale network featuring simplified QKD transmitters. We accomplish a per-user secure key rate of >339 b/s in a dual-user scenario over a shared 12.8 km feeder and can further support a reach of up to 32.3 km in a single-user scenario. In addition, we compare our MRR to a conventional delay interferometer (DI) based QKD receiver, demonstrating no QBER penalty.

2. Simplified DPS-QKD with Shared Analyser

Taking the optical x-haul segment of 6G as an example, classical optics rely on no more than simple DML/EML optics that are paired with PIN-/APD-based receivers. Figure 1a sketches the link architecture. Depending on the degree of fiber scarcity [10], the x-haul typically relies on grey point-to-point or CWDM-assisted feeder links between the mobile edge cloud (MEC) and its remote radio heads (RRH). In contrary to the access domain, the optical budget is not the main concern due to the split-less network layout. In this context, QKD needs to adapt to (i) the chosen multiplexing strategy and (ii) the functional fronthaul split, meaning that network functions that greatly contribute to a complexity burden are being centralized at the MEC.

Fig. 1: (a) QKD-enhanced 6G-scale network and (b) DPS-QKD link architecture with shared multi-channel analyser.

Towards this notion, we gracefully introduce QKD by proposing a wavelength-cyclic DPS-QKD scheme (Fig. 1b). This approach leverages greatly simplified DPS transmitters at the RRHs while pooling SPAD-based QKD receivers at the MEC, where a compact multi-wavelength quantum state analyser is simultaneously processing WDM-aggregated DPS signals. A practical wavelength plan would motivate the use of the C-band for QKD, since broadband radio-over-fiber (RoF) transmission at 25 to 100 Gb/s is sensitive to dispersion-induced inter-symbol interference and would therefore prefer operation in the O-band [11].

3. Experimental Setup and PIC-Based Analyser

The experimental setup to evaluate the DPS-QKD performance with shared state analyser is presented in Fig. 2a. Alice uses a DFB laser at λ_{Q1} , which is tuned to a MRR resonance. A Mach-

Fig. 2: (a) Experimental DPS-QKD setup using the (b) SOI MRR as state analyser. (c) MRR through-port and (d) DI response.

Zehnder Modulator (MZM) and a phase modulator (PM) are used for pulse carving at 50% of the symbol width and for state encoding at $R_{\text{sym}} = 1$ Gbaud, respectively. These state encoders are driven by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG). A variable optical attenuator (VOA) then sets the launch power to an average photon number of $\mu_{\alpha} = 0.1$ $h\nu/\text{symbol}$. In the case of multiple DPS-QKD transmitters (γ) a second DFB laser at λ_{Q2} , together with a second VOA, is employed. For the sake of simplicity and due to the limited number of available AWG channels, 200-GHz add-drop multiplexers (MX) are used for multiplexing the active state encoder. To account for realistic conditions, λ_{Q1} and λ_{Q2} have been decorrelated through an optical delay line (τ) to emulate the generation of different keys.

The quantum signal transmission is then investigated for a back-to-back (b2b) scenario and over concatenated ITU-T G.652B compatible single-mode fiber (SMF) spools with a total length L of up to 69.8 km.

At Bob, the optical signal is either coupled to the PIC-based MRR (α) via grating couplers (1D-GC) or to a commercial 1 GHz DI (β), before the demodulated signal is detected via InGaAs SPADs. The MRR, presented in Fig. 2b, is realized on a silicon-on-insulator (SOI) platform. It features a radius of $200 \mu\text{m}$ and a waveguide cross-section of $500 \times 220 \text{ nm}^2$. We achieved a maximum transmission of -11.5 dB for fiber-to-fiber coupling over its through-port and the static extinction at its resonance is 24.3 dB for TE polarization (Fig. 2c). Its free spectral range (FSR) is 120.1 GHz and the FWHM bandwidth of the through-port notch is 0.27 GHz. The overall transmission spectrum is given by the spectral response of the grating couplers and spans over >50 nm, covering the entire C-band. The polarization dependence of the MRR is addressed through a polarization controllers at each Alice. Figure 2d shows the transmission of the DI. It features a static extinction ratio of 22 dB, a FSR of 1 GHz, a FWHM bandwidth of 72 MHz and an insertion loss (IL) of ~ 0.8 dB.

A MX is employed for quantum signal demultiplexing before SPAD detection and the detection events for each wavelength λ_{Qi} are recorded by a time-tagging module (TTM). We then performed frame synchronization, temporal filtering at 20% of the symbol width and a real-time raw key rate (RKR) and QBER evaluation, followed by an off-line secure key rate (SKR) estimation. The employed SPADs featured dark count rates of 466 and 472 cts/s, a detection efficiency of 10% and a dead-time of $25 \mu\text{s}$.

Fig. 3: RKR, QBER and SKR as functions of the optical link budget for (a) silicon MRR and (b) DI as shared quantum state analyzer for the back-to-back scenario, (c, d) over SMF transmission and (e, f) time-resolved QKD performance.

Fig. 4: (a) Wavelength dependence of QKD performance and spectra for (b) single- and (c) dual-channel state preparation before single-photon leveling. (d) Time-resolved QKD performance for simultaneous dual-wavelength demodulation.

4. QKD Performance and Multi- λ Operation

Figures 3a and 3b present the RKR, QBER, and SKR performance for $\lambda_{Q1} = 1550.5$ nm as a function of the optical budget (OB) for the b2b link using the MRR- (\blacklozenge) and DI-assisted (\blacktriangle) receivers. At an OB of 0 dB, we reach RKR of 11.4 kb/s and 10.8 kb/s at QBERs of 3.94% and 3.70% for the MRR and DI, respectively. In both cases the QBER is below the QBER threshold of 5% [12], which we consider the limit for secure key extraction for our coherent-state DPS-QKD implementation. The estimated SKRs for MRR and DI are 1.56 kb/s and 1.80 kb/s. The earlier saturation of the SPAD for the DI-assisted receiver for an OB ≤ 0 , corresponding to $\mu_Q \geq 0.1$ h ν /symbol, can be attributed to the wider eye-diagram of the DI output (Fig. 2d) compared to the MRR (Fig. 2c): Due to the applied temporal filtering of the detection events during post-processing, a higher share of detected photons is cut in case of the DI than for the MRR, yielding a lower RKR despite its lower IL. The achievable total OB before surpassing the QBER threshold confirms this, since the threshold is reached at similar RKR of 7.8 kb/s and 8.4 kb/s for different OBs of 5.3 dB and 16.3 dB in case of MRR and DI, respectively. The difference in RKR at this point can be attributed to the 2.3 dB higher extinction ratio of the MRR. Therefore, the performance of the MRR- and DI-assisted receivers are comparable in terms of QBER, which is supported by the similar OBs of 16 dB and 16.3 dB for the MRR and DI when assuming an identical IL of 0.8 dB.

Figures 3c and 3d discuss the achievable link reach before surpassing the QBER threshold. The MRR state analyser supports secure key generation up to 32.3 km, while the DI permits a reach of up to 58.8 km, due to its larger OB. These values correspond to 8.9 dB and 16.3 dB of fiber loss, given an average fiber loss of 0.277 dB/km as it applies to our concatenated lab fibers. We attribute the 3.6 dB of increased optical budget for the MRR-based receiver and SMF transmission to a better allocation of the laser to the MRR resonance.

The time-resolved QKD performance, reported in Fig. 3e and 3f for a typical 6G x-haul reach of 12.8 km, clearly shows the advantage of the compact MRR in terms of stability when compared to the DI with its larger footprint. While both demodulating elements are temperature-stabilized with 0.1 °C precision, the secure key generation with the MRR-assisted receiver shows no sign of instability. On the contrary, the DI drifts quickly and requires manual re-alignment (δ) through laser tuning.

We next investigated the performance of the MRR to demodulate quantum signals at various C-band wavelengths λ_{Q1} reaching from 1534.3 to 1555.3 nm (Fig. 4a), for which the corresponding DFB sources have been tuned to the respective resonances of the same MRR (Fig. 2c). An exemplary spectrum of an optical carrier λ_{Q1} with and without DPS modulation (ξ) is shown in Fig. 4b. The performance of all 13 tested channels is comparable and reaches an average SKR of 1.33 ± 0.17 kb/s. This proves the silicon MRR as simple, compact and stable demodulation element that can simultaneously process the received signals from different QKD users in a WDM-centric deployment scenario.

We finally investigated the simultaneous demodulation of two quantum channels at $\lambda_{Q2} = 1548.5$ and $\lambda_{Q1} = 1550.5$ nm (Fig. 4c) through the MRR, employing one SPAD per user. We achieve average RKR of 10 kb/s and 9.8 kb/s at QBERs of 4.81% and 4.77% for λ_{Q1} and λ_{Q2} for a fiber length of 12.8 km. This corresponds to SKRs of 339 b/s and 384 b/s per user, which is sufficient to secure 4 Tb/s/user of classical data traffic considering the AES-GCM limit for single-key use over TLS 1.3 [13].

5. Conclusion

We have demonstrated the feasibility of MRR-assisted DPS-QKD for wavelength-agnostic secure key generation, featuring up to 13 C-band WDM channels that span over 21 nm. Moreover, simultaneous state analysis in a highly compact demodulator has been demonstrated for a dual-user scenario. We

believe that cost-sharing of centralized QKD elements, together with distributed QKD transmitters with a telecom-centric optics layout can enable the simplified integration of QKD within 6G x-haul links.

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